

Character Based Learning Improvement to Increase Mathematic Study Result in Pgri Junior High School Jakarta

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Abstract:- Within the days currently we have to validation every students education. One of method we use Character Based Learning, overall we not only give one direction lesson to students in junior high school PGRI. Although we also combine with character building as long teachers creativity and competency students can easier understand Mathematics from interaction in class.

Keywords:- Character Based Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the National Education System Law No. 20 of 2003 mandates that National Education functions to develop capabilities and shape dignified national character and civilization in order to educate the life of the nation, aims to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, competent, creative, independent and become a democratic and responsible citizen.

School is a place of education for the formation of the character of students. Here students are required to increase the intensity and quality in developing their abilities. This demand is based on a growing social phenomenon, namely the increase in juvenile delinquency in society, ranging from brawls, beatings, theft, robbery and immoral acts. This phenomenon has reached a troubling level (Dewi, 2015). Therefore, schools as the official forum for fostering the younger generation are expected to increase their role in shaping the personality of students in addition to the family and society. To prevent the moral crisis from getting worse in the younger generation, character education can be integrated into every subject, including mathematics. Mathematics learning is an integral part of the education system in schools and is given from elementary to secondary education, even in higher education.

For schools and especially teachers, willingness and hard work in innovating in learning like this is something that must be done, in addition to achieving learning goals that are cognitive in nature which until now is still quite a tough task, especially for teachers of general subjects, like math. This paper will provide an overview of how character education can be developed in learning mathematics. The problem that often arises is competition in education which is considered

to be of good quality, sometimes something is forgotten, namely how to build a nation's children with character.

What does it mean to have students who are smart, but like to lie, be dishonest, and dare to parents and teachers. In building the character of education in schools, there are three most important pillars. The foundations that schools already have are vision, mission and goals. The foundation above is commitment, motivation, and togetherness. The pillars used to realize character learning include three things. First, build character, personality, or morals. Second, develop multiple intelligences. Third, the meaningfulness of learning. In order for the three pillars to remain on a solid foundation, there is continuous control, evaluation and improvement (Najib Sulhan, M.A, 2009: 6-7).

❖ *Student Character Education in Mathematics Learning*

A. *Definition of Character*

Character according to Alwisol (2008: 8) is a description of behavior that highlights right-wrong, good-bad values, both explicitly and implicitly. Character is different from personality, because the notion of personality is freed from values. However, both personality and character are in the form of behavior shown to the social environment. Both are relatively permanent and guide, direct and organize individual activities. So the term character relates to a person's personality. A person can be called a person of character if his behavior is in accordance with moral principles. Meanwhile, according to Wibowo (2013: 12) character is a natural trait of the human soul that characterizes a person in acting and interacting in the family and in society.

B. *Character Education*

According to Samani and Hariyanto (2013: 45) in their book explaining that character education is the process of providing guidance to students to become whole human beings with character in the dimensions of heart, mind, body and feeling and intention. Whereas character education according to Zubaedi (2012: 19) is all business planning carried out by teachers that can influence the formation of the character of their students, understand, shape, and foster ethical values as a whole

C. The Results of Learning Mathematics

Learning outcomes can be understood from the two words that make it up, namely "results" and "learning". The definition of results refers to an acquisition as a result of carrying out a process activity that results in a functional change of input (Purwanto, 2009:4).

While learning is essentially a "change" that occurs within a person after the end of the learning process. So learning outcomes are a change in behavior that occurs after participating in the teaching and learning process in accordance with educational goal.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses classroom action research (CAR), the research model refers to Arikunto's model (2008) which includes 4 steps. the research was carried out in mathematics subjects. The research population was class VIII students at SMP PGRI 12 South Jakarta, totaling 120 students in the 2021-2022 academic year, odd semester. The data was collected using random sampling, with a total of 20 students. Classroom action research is carried out in the form of a cycle consisting of four stages in PGRI junior high school, namely planning, implementing actions/actions, observation, and reflection. Research should be managed on the basis of a healthy partnership (collaborative), so that both parties can reap the reciprocity of benefits.

Through the design of class action research / PTK (classroom action research) learning problems can be studied and resolved, so that innovative learning processes and achievement of learning objectives can be actualized systematically. Based on the description above, it is clear that PTK is a form of reflective study by action actors, especially teachers in the classroom, to increase the rational stability of their actions in carrying out learning, deepen understanding of the actions taken, and improve where practices are carried out. learning practices implemented.

This research was conducted through a process of collaboration between mathematics teachers and researchers. There are several experts who put forward an action research model with a different chart, but in general there are four stages that are commonly passed, namely (Arikunto, 2012: 16): 1. Planning (planning) 2. Implementation (action) 3. Observation (observation)) 4. Reflection

The design of this research is a class action research with a flow of activities following the Lewin Model design. This classroom action in PGRI research is descriptive qualitative in nature. Primary data sources are researchers who take action and students who receive action, while secondary data is in the form of documentation data. Data collection can be done with observation techniques, interviews, and documentation. The data analysis technique used in this research is qualitative data analysis, which follows the concept given by Hiles and Huberman in Arikunto (2011:37). The steps for data analysis and interactive models can be explained as follows: a) data collection, b) data reduction, c) data presentation, and d) conclusion drawing and verification. Performance indicators in this study include: (1) Student activity in working on the exercises given; (2) students' ability to complete questions on time; (3) Completeness of student learning outcomes.

III. RESULT

Table 1 We have standard for Exam pass points :

Grading	Grading Value	Exam Result
		0-100 Point
A	4,0	90-100,0
A-	3,75	80-89,99
B+	3,25	76-79,99
B	3,0	72-75,99
B-	2,75	68-71,99
C+	2,25	62-67,99
C	2,0	56-61,99
D	1	45-55,99
E	0	0-44,99

The results of individual student PGRI Junior high school observation data are in table 1. It can be seen in the appendix and the percentage results per aspect of student learning activities classically can be seen in table 2 within

Table 2 : Learning Activity in 1st Cylce

Evaluation Aspect	Score Value			Students Qty	Category
	Low	Medium	High		
Task Finish Score	5	22	6	20	Good
Pre Exam Score	3	18	11	20	Good
Solve Test in Class	10	14	16	20	Medium
Active in Class	10	16	16	20	Medium
Total	24	66	50	20	Medium

As can be seen from table 2, 5 students obtained low scores for assignments, 22 students for moderate scores, and 6 students for high assignment scores were classified as good. As for the low value aspects of the practice questions, 3 students were obtained, the discussion value aspects were 18 students, and the high value aspects of the problem practice were 11 students. The score for doing the exercise in front of the low class is 10, the presentation score is 14, and the score for doing the exercise in front of the high class is

16, while the activeness aspect in the low class is 10 students, the activeness aspect in the medium class is 16, and the active aspect in the high class is 16 student. Cycle II action activities ended by guiding students to conclude the lesson, then the teacher gave a post test to students to see the completeness of student learning outcomes. Based on the assessment results of assignment scores and semester final exams in PGRI Junior high school, students who achieved learning mastery in cycle II had increased compared to learning outcomes in cycle 1 combined with creativity teacher include presence campaign. So classical mastery in cycle II had been achieved/good.

Table 3 : Learning Activity in 2nd Cylce

Evaluation Aspect	Score Value			Students Qty	Category
	Low	Medium	High		
Task Finish Score	3	9	21	20	Good
Pre Exam Score	3	11	17	20	Good
Solve Test in Class	2	20	9	20	Good
Active in Class	6	13	15	20	Good
Total	14	53	62	20	Good

Can be seen from table 3. For low assignment scores, 2 students were obtained, 9 students had moderate scores, and 21 students had high assignment scores, which were classified as good. As for the low value aspect of the practice questions, 3 students obtained, the moderate discussion value aspect 11 students, and the high discussion value aspect 17 students. For low class presentation PGRI Junior high school scores of 2, scores for working on questions in front of medium class are 20, and scores for working on questions in front of high class are 9, while aspects of activeness in low class are 6 students, aspects of activeness in middle class are 13, and aspects of activeness in class 15 students high. This submit with related school purpose in maintain education with creativity together.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research conducted, the conclusions are obtained as :

- The use of character-based learning based on this research can improve students' mathematics learning outcomes, namely from the first cycle being moderate, in the second cycle it has increased to be good at PGRI Junior high school.
- Education is a planned innovation to create a learning atmosphere and learning cycle so that students actively develop their own potential. The teacher's important role is to help, educate and guide and plan to create a pleasant learning atmosphere, process learning so that students are active in learning mathematics well within creativity and ownership not for student only.

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